

Copper(II), Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Manganese(II), Zinc(II), Iron(III), Cobalt(III), Manganese(III), Vanadium(IV), Thorium(IV) and Uranium(VI) Complexes of *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine

N. THANKARAJAN* and K. MOHANAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut, Kerala-673 635

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N-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine has been isolated as its stabler potassium salt, which yielded Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} , Zn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{III} , Mn^{III} , V^{IV} , Th^{IV} and U^{VI} complexes. These were characterised through their elemental, analytical, molar conductance, magnetic susceptibility and thermogravimetric data. On the basis of uv, ir and nmr spectral evidences, the ligand moiety has been shown to exist predominatingly in the quinone-amine form and to bond to metal ions through its quinone oxygen, deprotonated amino nitrogen and a carboxylate oxygen. This structure is supported also by available crystallographic data of related complexes.

AS compared to *N*-salicylideneamino acids, *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amino acids have received less attention as ligands¹. The scanty work reported on complexes of the latter type of ligands is mostly extension of the more detailed work carried out with the corresponding salicylidene bases. In the present investigation, potassium salt and metal chelates of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine (LH_2) have been isolated, and studied with special reference to the tautomeric structure of the ligand moiety in the metal complexes.

Experimental

Chemicals used were either AnalaR or G R. (E. Merck) quality reagents. Organic solvents, purified by standard methods², were employed.

Synthesis of potassium salt of ligand: It was synthesised by the reported method³.

Syntheses of metal complexes:

***Aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]copper(II), [$\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$]:** An aqueous solution (30 ml) of copper(II) sulphate pentahydrate (1.24 g, 0.005 mol), was added to a hot magnetically stirred solution (70 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (1.34 g, 0.005 mol) in 90% ethanol, after adjusting pH of the latter to 7–7.5 with acetic acid. The green solution obtained was refluxed on a water-bath for 1 h. A green product which separated was filtered, washed successively with water, and ether and dried in vacuum.

***Aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]iron(II), [$\text{Fe}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$]:** An aqueous solution (30 ml) of iron(II) ammonium sulphate hexahydrate

(1.96 g, 0.005 mol) was added in small portions to a magnetically stirred methanolic solution (70 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (1.34 g, 0.005 mol, $\text{pH} \sim 7$). A deep reddish violet solution obtained was stirred further for 3 h, filtered and the filtrate concentrated in vacuum to about 30 ml. The solution when cooled in ice, yielded deep reddish violet crystals, which were filtered, washed with water and ether, and dried in vacuum.

***Aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]cobalt(II), [$\text{Co}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$]:** To a refluxing solution (100 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (2.67 g, 0.01 mol, $\text{pH} \sim 7$) in 95% methanol was added gradually an aqueous solution of cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.49 g, 0.01 mol). After refluxing further for 2 h, the solution was concentrated to about 50 ml on a water-bath and then cooled in ice. Reddish brown crystals obtained were filtered, washed with water and ether, and dried in vacuum.

***Aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]nickel(II), [$\text{Ni}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$] and *aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]manganese(II), [$\text{Mn}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$]:** The complexes were prepared similarly as the cobalt(II) complex.

***Aqua*[*N*-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]zinc(II), [$\text{Zn}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{O})$]:** To a magnetically stirred hot solution (100 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (2.67 g, 0.01 mol, $\text{pH} \sim 7$ in 90% ethanol) was added slowly an aqueous solution (20 ml) of zinc(II) acetate dihydrate (2.19 g, 0.01 mol). After further stirring for 6 h, the contents were filtered and the filtrate concentrated over a water-bath to about 50 ml. On allowing the solution to cool, pale yellow crystals were obtained, which were filtered, washed with water and ether, and dried in vacuum.

Potassium bis[N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]ferrate(III) monohydrate, $K[Fe(L)_2]H_2O$: It was prepared from iron(III) ammonium sulphate hydrate by the same method used for preparing iron(II) complex except that 1:2 metal—ligand ratio was maintained. Dark brown crystals obtained were recrystallised from methanol.

S dium bis[N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]cobaltate(III) monohydrate, $Na[Co(L)_2]H_2O$: To the carbonate complex, $Na_2[Co(CO_3)] \cdot 3H_2O$, (1.8 g, 0.005 mol) refluxed in methanol (70 ml) was added a methanolic solution (50 ml) of sodium salt of the ligand (0.01 mol, obtained *in situ*, pH ~5.5) in small portions. After continued refluxing for 4 h, the mixture was filtered, and the filtrate concentrated over a water-bath to about 30 ml. Brown crystals obtained on subsequent cooling in ice, was filtered, sucked dry and recrystallised from methanol.

Potassium bis[N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]manganate(III) monohydrate, $K[Mn(L)_2]H_2O$: A methanolic solution of manganese(III) acetate dihydrate (1.33 g, 0.005 mol, 50 ml) prepared by the reported method⁴ was added gradually to a magnetically stirred solution (50 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (2.67 g, 0.01 mol, pH ~7) in 90% methanol. The mixture was stirred for 3 h, and the filtrate concentrated over a water-bath to about 25 ml. This solution on allowing to cool, yielded dark yellow crystals, which were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried in vacuum.

Aqua [N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]oxovanadium(IV), $[VO(L)(H_2O)]$: It was prepared from oxovanadium(IV) sulphate hydrate, similarly as the copper(II) complex. When the reaction mixture contained pyridine (10 ml), a dark green pyridine adduct was also obtained.

Aqua [N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]dioxouranium(VI), $[UO_2(L)(H_2O)]$: To a hot magnetically stirred solution (50 ml) of potassium salt of the ligand (1.34 g, 0.005 mol, pH ~7) in 90% methanol was added gradually an aqueous solution (20 ml) of dioxouranium(VI) nitrate hexahydrate (2.51 g, 0.005 mol). A reddish brown product separated out immediately. After continued stirring and heating for 3 h, the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed with water and ether, and vacuum dried.

Bis[N-(2-oxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato]thorium(IV) monohydrate, $[Th(L)_2]H_2O$: A methanolic solution (50 ml) of the potassium salt (2.67 g, 0.01 mol, pH ~4) of the ligand and an aqueous solution (10 ml) of thorium(IV) nitrate hexahydrate (2.94 g, 0.005 mol) when mixed, yielded a yellow product. After stirring the mixture further for 30 min, the complex was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and sucked dry.

Analysis and measurements: Infrared spectra in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP3-300 spectrophotometer. Far-ir spectra

were recorded on a Polytec FIR 30 Fourier spectrometer using CsI disc. Nmr were recorded on a Varian XL-100 FT spectrometer using TMS as reference. Uv-vis spectra were recorded on a Pye Unicam SP 1800 spectrophotometer. Stanton TR-1 pen recording thermobalance was used for thermogravimetric analysis. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy magnetic balance using $Hg[Co(NCS)_4]$ as standard.

Results and Discussion

The analytically pure complexes are listed in Table 1. All the complexes are stable at room temperature and have good keeping qualities. Formulation of the complexes has been on the basis of their analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data (Table 1). The complexes depicted as ionic are, as expected, soluble in water. Thermogravimetric analysis showed that a water molecule is preferentially lost from the aqua-complexes in the temperature range 180–200°. The complex hydrates were dehydrated at 90–110°.

Tautomeric structure of ligand: A comparison of the uv spectra of potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate (λ_{max} 415 nm, ϵ 8 × 10⁴; λ_{max} 345 nm, ϵ 1 006) and potassium *N*-salicylidene-glycinate (λ_{max} 330, ϵ 9 185; λ_{max} 410 nm, ϵ 985) in ethanol revealed that these compounds exist predominantly as quinoneamine and phenolimine, respectively⁵. These structures persist in the solid state also, as revealed by uv spectra of the compounds recorded in nujol.

Conclusive evidence regarding the quinoneamine structure of *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate is provided by its ¹H nmr spectra in DMSO-d₆, which showed clearly the presence of CH—NH—CH₂ grouping. Signals of CH and CH₂ protons are doublets centred at δ 8.81 and 3.87, respectively. In view of the occurrence of these doublets, the broad multiplet observed at δ 13.71 must necessarily be assigned to the NH proton of quinoneamine form. Integrated intensities of the signals agreed with the number of proton(s) of each type. Since even weak signals for phenolimine form could not be detected in the spectra, it should be concluded that quinoneamine form vastly predominates in solution. Quinoneamine structure has been previously suggested for *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amines⁶.

Infrared spectral data are also quite in agreement with the above structure. Spectra of potassium *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinate showed a strong band at 1 640 cm^{-1} , with no other band at higher frequency in the double bond region. Taking into account the uv and nmr spectral evidences, this band gets undoubtedly assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$ of the quinoneamine form. Such low carbonyl stretching frequency can not be accounted for adequately on the basis of conjugation and internal hydrogen bonding. Contribution from immonium naphtholate form, therefore, seems probable. Thus, analogous compounds like 1-phenylazo-2-naphthalenol⁷

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF METAL CHELATES OF *N*-(2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHYLIDENE)GLYCINE

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		μ_{eff} B.M.	Molar conductance $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
	O	N		
[Cu(L)(H ₂ O)]	50.72 (50.55)	4.44 (4.54)	1.81	1.71
[Fe(L)(H ₂ O)]	51.90 (51.84)	4.65 (4.65)	5.12	2.30
[Co(L)(H ₂ O)]	51.27 (51.31)	4.50 (4.60)	4.71	2.10
[Ni(L)(H ₂ O)]	51.64 (51.35)	4.50 (4.61)	3.00	1.91
[Mn(L)(H ₂ O)]	52.19 (52.00)	4.60 (4.67)	5.85	3.00
[Zn(L)(H ₂ O)]	50.37 (50.25)	4.39 (4.51)	Dia	2.70
K[Fe(L) ₂]H ₂ O	55.29 (55.02)	5.02 (4.94)	5.92	89.27
Na[Co(L) ₂]H ₂ O	56.27 (56.31)	5.20 (5.05)	Dia	90.68
K[Mn(L) ₂]H ₂ O	55.48 (55.10)	4.71 (4.95)	5.01	87.68
[VO(L)(H ₂ O)]	49.80 (49.99)	4.57 (4.49)	1.70	1.80
[Th(L) ₂]H ₂ O	44.59 (44.31)	3.82 (3.98)	Dia	0.91
[UO ₂ (L)(H ₂ O)]	30.40 (30.20)	2.81 (2.71)	Dia	3.30

and 1-nitroso-2-naphthalenol⁸ for which also similar zwitterionic contributing structures are possible, show still lower carbonyl stretching frequencies, (~ 1625 and 1620 cm^{-1} , respectively). Two strong bands presumably due to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ are observed at 1600 and 1380 cm^{-1} , respectively. The $\Delta\nu$ of 220 cm^{-1} can be taken as evidence for strong hydrogen bonding of the NH with the carboxylate ion⁹. Because of this strong bond, the quinone oxygen can form only a weak bifurcated hydrogen bond, if at all. This adequately explains why the quinone carbonyl stretching frequency observed for the compound is higher than that of the analogous compounds. As may be expected for strongly hydrogen bonded NH, there is a broad band extending from 3450 to 2500 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the compound. This band almost completely conceals bands due to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$. The medium intense band at 1545 cm^{-1} , amidst bands due to skeletal vibrations of the aryl ring, is attributable to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$.

It is interesting to note that *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)amines exist in the quinoneimine form (Fig. 1) despite the fact that in this tautomeric form, aromaticity of one of the condensed aryl rings is compromised. The greater stability of this form over the naphthylimine form appears due partly to

 Fig. 1. *N*-(2-Hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycinato.

contribution from zwitterionic immonium naphtholate form, and partly to strong internal hydrogen bonding under resonant conditions. Displacement of tautomeric equilibrium towards quinoneimine form on passing from *N*-salicylidene bases to their bicyclic homologues may be attributed to the fall in redox potential of the corresponding quinone¹⁰.

Tautomeric structure of the ligand moiety in metal complexes :

Uv spectra : Uv spectra of the metal chelates reveal that 415 nm band of potassium salt of the ligand is shifted only marginally. This is indicative of the quinoneimine structural form of the ligand in the metal complexes also⁸.

Ir spectra : The quinone carbonyl band of the ligand at 1645 cm^{-1} is missing in the spectra of the metal complexes. However, the strong $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ band at $\sim 1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has a shoulder on the higher wave number side ($\sim 1620 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) which in all likelihood, is the carbonyl band of the ligand, shifted through coordination. The $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{COO})$ band has also another shoulder on the lower wave number side ($\sim 1575 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributable to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$. The upward shift of this frequency is presumably due to increased chelate ring resonance. A strong $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{COO})$ band is observed at 1380 cm^{-1} . The $\Delta\nu(\text{COO})$ value of 220 cm^{-1} is indicative of monodentate bonding by the carboxylate⁹. Although the broad $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ band of the ligand clears from the lower wavenumber region ($3100-2500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), broad bands of varying intensity appear in the higher wavenumber region ($3600-3100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), due to coordinated water or water of hydration in the metal complexes.

Further evidence for bonding by nitrogen and oxygen atoms is provided by far-ir spectra of the complexes, which show medium intense broad band at $450-530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ν_{M-N} , and bands at $350-440\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable¹¹ to ν_{M-O} . Oxovanadium(II) complex shows $\nu_{V=O}$ at 990 cm^{-1} . It has been reported that the position of this band depends on the nature and number of other ligands present¹². The pyridine adduct, accordingly shows depressed $\nu_{V=O}$ at 950 cm^{-1} . A strong band at 915 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of dioxouranium(II) complex¹³ is attributable to $\nu_{\text{asym}}(\text{UO}_2)$. Absence of band at $\sim 860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{UO}_2)$ is indicative of linear UO_2 .

Nmr spectra: Nmr spectra of the cobalt(III) and dioxouranium(II) complexes recorded in DMSO-d_6 did not show any NH proton signal, but revealed singlet signals for the aldehydic and the methylene protons at $\sim \delta 8.8$ and 3.8 , respectively.

All the above spectral data indicate that *N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)glycine acts in the metal complexes as dibasic tridentate, and bonds to the metal ions through its quinone oxygen, deprotonated amino nitrogen and a carboxylate oxygen (Fig. 2). This representation is in full accord with the available crystallographic data of metal chelates of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

Fig. 2. Structure of the ligand moiety in the metal chelates.

Thus, for dimeric copper(II) chelate of [*N*-(2-hydroxy-1-naphthylidene)]-2-hydroxy-1-naphthylmethyl-

amine¹⁴, the phenolic C—O ($1.31, 1.24\text{ \AA}$) is shorter than the azomethine C—N ($1.35, 1.30\text{ \AA}$). Despite the somewhat low precision of this analysis, it is difficult to reconcile with the above data without recourse to the quinoneimine structure of the ligand moiety in the metal complex.

Ligand moieties in metal chelates of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, have so far been represented only in the naphtholimine form. This erroneous representation, which stands corrected as a result of this investigation, seems to have arisen from their formal similarity with metal chelates of *N*-salicylidene bases. The latter ligands exist in phenolimine form in their free and complexed states¹⁵.

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